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RANDOM NUMBER GENERATION TO ENSURE INFORMATION SECURITY ON MOBILE PHONES

Nurullaev Mirkhon Muhammadovich

Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute, Uzbekistan

nurullayevmirxon@gmail.com

Abstract: The article will discuss the features of generating random bits on mobile devices based on gyroscope, magnetometer, accelerometer sensors and the role that these random numbers occupy in information security. The random bit generator uses smartphone sensors as a source of entropy. A mobile software is created, which states that the results obtained are verified by NIST statistical tests.

Keywords: random bits, gyroscope, magnetometer, accelerometer, mobile device, sensor.

The cryptographic strength of cryptographic systems is determined by the algorithm used in them and the cryptographic strength of the key in it [1]. And the generation of a cryptographic key is directly related to randomly generated numbers.

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has developed a set of statistical tests for random and pseudorandom number generators in cryptography. These tests allow us to evaluate random bits [2]. A random bit generator extracts raw data from various entropy sources. The paper [3] proposes principles for constructing entropy sources for a random bit generator, requirements for them and tests for checking entropy sources. Data from the entropy source is processed using deterministic generators before application [4].

One of the main requirements for a random bit generator is the inability to predict in advance the bits generated by the generator. The paper [5] presents a study on predicting a random sequence. The paper [6] presents a software method for quickly checking a random sequence for randomness. This software method is used to evaluate random bits. Usually the OpenSSL library is used to generate

random numbers on the Android platform. Separately, it should be noted that [7] in the work we can witness a vulnerability found in the OpenSSL library when generating random numbers on the Android platform.

The values obtained from smartphone sensors should not be used directly in cryptography. They should be processed based on a random number generator and/or hashing algorithms [8]. Using only hash algorithms, it is difficult to get high scores in NIST statistical tests [2], [9].

Considering that many smartphones are equipped with gyroscope, magnetometer and accelerometer sensors, in the proposed algorithm these sensors are used as sources of entropy.

An attempt to change the environment using various manipulations, when the accelerometer is used to generate random bits, the entropy of a stationary accelerometer cannot be reduced [10]. In mobile operating systems, mobile applications must have permission for this sensor in order to use the sensor as a source of entropy (for example, a camera [11], a wireless network, a microphone) [12]. Allowing a mobile application to allow only a few sensors to generate random bits is not considered an acceptable method for security reasons.

Software for generating random bits

Based on the above information, software has been developed for mobile phones running the Android operating system. In the mobile application, one or more sensors are selected to be used as an entropy source and the number of random bits to be generated is displayed. When the values of the gyroscope, magnetometer, accelerometer sensors change, the new values are transmitted to the random number generator. The mobile application will continue to read data from entropy sources until random bits are generated in the specified amount [13], [14], [15].

Random bits of a certain size were generated during the experiment. The generated random bits were checked based on NIST statistical tests. As a result of the verification, a sequence of random bits received a score of $P \geq 0.01$ from the tests, which means that random bits generated based on the proposed algorithm can be used in cryptography to generate cryptographic exchange keys (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Test result of generated random bits

The value of P is in the range from 0 to 1, and the closer it is to 1, the more random the sequence of bits is calculated. A distinctive feature of the generator is that it uses 4 sources of entropy. There is no way to predict the values of these entropy sources in advance. It also uses sensors available on almost all smartphones.

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“COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGIES”

International scientific and technical conference on October 14-15, 2022.

Web: <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/>

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